

Deliverable report for

Sustainable Energy Harvesting Systems Based on Innovative Mine Waste Recycling

Project 101058632

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Acronym	Description
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IoT	Internet of Things
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
TE	Thermoelectric, Thermoelectrics, Thermoelectricity
TEG	Thermoelectric Generators
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WP	Work Package
zT	Dimensionless figure of merit used to quantify the performance of thermoelectric materials

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Report on the Foresight exercise (Deliverable 7.1) of the START project demonstrates the foresight methods, processes, results and conclusions that derived from the interaction between the consortium and external experts in the fields of thermoelectric energy, raw materials science, sustainability and other areas relevant for the project.

In Task 7.1 (Foresight exercise for the development of a flexible, scalable and adaptable business case design for the START value chain) of Work Package 7 (Innovation and Exploitation strategy), the goal was to map possible thermoelectric-based value chains built around the START concepts, while at the same time identifying ways to keep the value chains flexible, scalable and adaptable for future implementation.

The foresight exercise implemented made use of Focus Group sessions and Delphi Surveys and developed towards the engagement with experts to understand their views and opinions on the thermoelectric technology as a whole, and in START in particular. The exercises targeted near and mid-term time horizons. Data collected through these foresight-adapted methods was complemented with desk research. The foresight exercises also informed the creation of a value chain and identified uncertainties crucial for START's innovation strategy. It outlined the framework for tetrahedrite-based thermoelectric devices, analyzed key activities, and addressed uncertainties affecting START and thermoelectrics. Flexibility in the value chain and application mapping were discussed, aiming to enhance START's value and commercialization strategies.

The Focus Groups, Delphi Surveys and Interviews show that experts believe that, in general, the START concept and approach are of great value to the thermoelectric and renewable energy communities and that the realization of tetrahedrite-based TE devices can become a commercial reality in the short to medium term, sustained with a well-developed value chain that considers a wide range of stakeholders. With the opinions and contributions from the experts it was possible to draft the main aspects of a START-based value chain that shall be considered, including Pros, Cons, Trends and further focus points.

With the support of experts, recommendations for short and medium timeframes were gathered that can make the value chain more flexible, scalable and leading to adaptable business case designs. Some of these recommendations include:

- Securing the tetrahedrite supply from more than one mine in Europe;
- Along with the application and use of tetrahedrite materials, study and consideration of other materials is necessary for better cost/value outputs;
- The use of synthetic tetrahedrite may be considered in case of unfavourable characteristics and overall output of natural tetrahedrites in certain modules;
- The main focus of START needs to be in developing a complete assembly of a TE module into a large scale TEG tile and integrate it into a system for application;
- START needs to enable the establishment and access to rapid and mass manufacturing of materials and devices;
- The system integration aspect has been missing from the focus, which shall be included;
- Resources can be considered for developing START's own heat exchangers or other energy conversion equipment, instead of acquiring these from third parties;

- The risk of being outcompeted by incumbent technologies or alternative solutions within an application segment shall be mapped;
- The START ecosystem needs to invest resources in raising and increasing awareness of the market for TEs;
- The option of a fully digitized value chain shall be examined;
- An application area with high potential is linked to remote areas and standalone situations, where grid electricity is not available.

The next steps in the innovation and exploitation process will be dedicated to the qualification and the quantification of device performances and the identification of commercial parameters for the START technological aspects.

2 INTRODUCTION

This report showcases the foresight exercises developed with internal and external START experts in efforts of drafting an initial LogFrame (Logical Framework) of a business model for a flexible, scalable, adaptable mineral-derived value chain that START is to build. The main goal is to enhance the value of the START products, services and ultimately, business case, while identifying the strong points and uncertainties in the business and commercialisation strategies that are to be developed.

To map the flexibility in the value chain design, the work structure made use of foresight adapted exercises in the form of Focus Group Sessions and Delphi Surveys. These were used with four main goals in mind. First, to recognize the major uncertainties the START technology components are likely to encounter. Second, to identify the specific parts of the value chain system that may provide the kind of flexibility best suited to deal with the uncertainties recognized in previous step. Third, to evaluate alternative flexible design and incorporate the best into the value chain design. Fourth, to plan for eventual implementation of the chosen flexibilities by both making arrangements with the stakeholders in the process and monitoring the conditions that would indicate whether and when to exercise the design flexibility and adapt the system to new circumstances.

The European Foresight Platform states that “A Foresight exercise usually produces both formal or tangible and informal or intangible outcomes. While formal outcomes are incorporated into products and deliverables, informal outcomes derive from the Foresight process itself.”¹. In the case of START, these formal outcomes are delivered: survey results, sectoral analysis and priority lists, among others. Informal outcomes are seen in the form of networking, consensus building, changing attitudes and mindsets and the integration of the foresight results in START and further activities within and outside of the project scope.

As the START Foresight exercises concerns the entire START value chain, all consortium members participated in their implementation, together with members of the Scientific Advisory Board, and the Exploitation and Commercialisation Committee. External experts representing all areas of the value chain were invited to participate ensuring full coverage of relevant scientific and business areas.

¹ <http://foresight-platform.eu/community/forlearn/why-do-foresight/rationale/>

3 METHODOLOGY

To arrive at the results from the foresight exercise, the following steps were taken:

1. Desk research
2. Focus Groups
3. Delphi Survey
4. Complementary interviews with experts

3.1 DESK RESEARCH

The preparation step to start the Foresight exercises was dedicated to desk research on the past and current status of thermoelectric energy as well as on future plans for this specific type of energy conversion technology. For this, a number of reports and scientific papers (including various roadmaps, foresight studies and reports from many projects and initiatives focusing on the relevant topics) were screened in a process that in foresight is known as Horizon Scanning.

These information sources were used for the following steps in the process. I.e., Focus Groups, Delphi Survey and the interviews were all built on the information collected and processed through the Horizon Scanning: orientation (what others are doing now, envisaging for the future), framing (what issues/topics they are focusing on) and stimulating discussion. The reviewed literature sources are listed in the References.

The review of the many literature sources highlighted a number of focus points that were further explored with the help of the Focus Groups and Delphi Surveys, spanning Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental and Legal aspects. Some of those points include:

- Sustainable material sources, use of toxic materials and costs
- Material stability and temperature range of operation
- Scalability of thermoelectric devices
- Efficiency of thermoelectric devices and competition with other energy sources
- Technical and integration challenges of devices and systems
- Environmental impact
- Commercialization and end-users awareness
- Regulatory and Policy Hurdles
- Green energy, energy harvesting and remote power generation

A spillover effect of this desk research process was the establishment of a pool of potential experts to be contacted for the foresight exercises and remaining relevant tasks of the Work Package.

3.2 FOCUS GROUPS

Focus Groups are one of the many ways to collect qualitative data for a project, product or service development and certification. A Focus Group is a method of research and data collection that works around raising discussions between a moderator and a small group of participants. They can be used with a number of goals including 1) collecting background data, 2) identifying barriers, bottlenecks or support for new ideas or 3) gathering impressions for end-users on a concept, among others.

In the START foresight process, the use of Focus Groups was done with the aim to bring together experts interested in thermoelectrics and related topics in general, and also in the START approach in particular. This meant that experts were able to assess the current and future implementation plan of START and how the plan can be improved, challenged or adapted for better and more significant impacts.

Three focus groups were held as part of the exercise, one in person and two online. The exercises were held during 2023, first in Madrid, together with the START consortium meeting (May 2023) and in September online. In total, 14 internal and external experts were involved in the Focus Groups.

The preparation of Focus Groups entailed:

1. Studying and choosing Focus Groups topics and questions:
 - a. Desk research and revision of START topics of relevance.
2. Selecting and inviting experts:
 - a. Selection based on experts' participation on START webinars, clustering and collected through desk research.
 - b. Invitations sent by email with follow-up on positive responses.
3. Preparation of administrative forms (GDPR, information on the Focus Groups) and the presentation with questions itself:
 - a. Development of a Consent Form.
 - b. Development of a Participant Information package.
 - c. Creation of a PowerPoint presentation with questions to drive Focus Groups discussions.
4. Arranging a date for the meeting:
 - a. Dates agreed amongst participants through Doodle pools.
5. Setting up the meeting at an online meeting platform:
 - a. Microsoft Teams was used for the Focus Groups sessions online, with each meeting being recorded.

Participants were adequately informed of the Focus Groups objectives, data collection and processing activities. Consent was collected from each participant for recording the sessions and using any quotes (if any) on this report.

3.2.1 Hosting Focus Groups in Madrid (Focus Groups #1)

The first Focus Group was hosted in Madrid, Spain, back-to-back with the START Project Consortium Meeting in May 2023. This session counted the presence of 7 internal and 1 external experts with backgrounds spanning geosciences, materials science, commercialisation and thermoelectrics.

The following questions were presented to and discussed with the participants:

1. What are the major uncertainties of Thermoelectrics and materials for TE value chains? What could happen that changes the TE value chain?

2. What kind of applications do you see as potential and promising based on TE materials? By which year do you think such application could reach the market?
3. Do you know of any new research results related to TE? Do you know of any new trends?
4. Do you believe that the future of TE-s could be based on tetrahedrites?
5. Would you be willing to pay more for a sustainable TE device? How much more?
6. Do you miss any elements from the START planned activities/focus?
7. What are your main doubts for the START approach?
8. What are the benefits that you expect could be for you from the START project? Any commercial ones?
9. Who could be interested in the START technological approach?
10. Would the appearance of a new, more efficient material, put START out of business? What could we plan/do for avoiding that?

Due to lack of time, some questions remained unaddressed, therefore experts were contacted after the session for providing their answers offline, as a follow-up measure.

Figure 1: Focus Groups session #1 in Madrid.

3.2.2 Hosting Focus Groups online (Focus Groups #2 and #3)

Focus Groups 2 and 3 were held online on the same day, 27th September 2023. Three external and one internal expert participated in each of these sessions.

The following questions were addressed to and discussed with the participants:

1. What are the big uncertainties of Thermoelectrics (TE) and materials for TE value chains? What could happen that changes the value chain?
2. What kind of applications do you see as potential and promising based on TE materials? By which year do you think such application could reach the market?
3. Do you know of any ongoing research or new results related to TE? Do you know of any new trends in TE?

4. Do you believe that the future of TE could be based on tetrahedrites?
5. Would you be willing to pay more for a sustainable TE device? How much more?
6. Do you miss any elements from the START planned activities/focus?
7. What are your main doubts for the START approach?
8. What are the benefits that you expect that you could gain/use from the START project? Any commercial ones?
9. Who (companies, research groups, field of expertise, etc.) could be interested in the START technological approach?
10. Would the appearance of a new, more efficient material, hinder START from becoming commercialised? If yes, what could we plan/do for avoiding that?

Due to lack of time, some questions remained unaddressed, therefore experts were contacted after the session for providing their answers offline, as a follow-up measure.

Figure 2: Focus Groups session #2, online.

Figure 3: Focus Groups session #3, online.

3.3 DELPHI SURVEY

The START project deployed the Delphi survey as a complementary foresight tool to measure the maturity of the project concept, providing chances for potential improvements that might become necessary along the project evolution, with major focus on the technological, business and economy aspects. The Delphi survey methodology has been designed as a forecasting technique to support technological development and implementation for many technology lines. The main aim is to drive the participants to a consensus on different topics, throughout statements and questions, made in two or more rounds. This technique is anonymous, building on group communication, so that the process is effective in allowing a group of individuals, as a whole, to deal with a complex problem or question (Linstone and Turoff, 2002). In a Delphi process, experts (the participants) are asked to consider and classify a number of questions or statements.

The Delphi process is different from other types of surveys and questionnaires. First, a list of relevant interested experts is pre-compiled. Second, there is a possibility for experts to comment and explain their opinion on any of the statements. Third, answers are analysed, statistics built and shared with the experts for further comments, resulting in new rounds of questions. Finally, the objective of a Delphi is to reach a consensus within the expert pool.

The START Delphi Survey was built in two rounds between the months of October 2023 and April 2024, with round 1 running between October and November 2023 and round 2 between March and April 2024. It was used as a way to engage with experts and collect their views and opinions in areas of interest to START and that are relevant for the project development both during and after the funding period. The survey ultimately addressed the current and future states of the thermoelectric field and the future of START, as a new technology line based on tetrahedrite thermoelectric modules and systems, entwined with topics such as sustainability, energy generation and economics.

3.3.1 Delphi Survey technical aspects

For the creation of the START Delphi Survey – both rounds – the EU Survey platform (<https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/>) was used. This platform allows for the proper development of Delphi statements and questions and data collection from experts while following EU's privacy guidelines for data collection and processing. Basic statistics and answers are collected by the platform and later treated. Further statistical analysis of the results was done with Microsoft Excel and with the help of online tools.

An experts' database was created to gather possible interested participants – START experts, consortium contacts, contacts from the Clustering and Focus Groups exercises, internet search on research and industry-relevant experts. This was coupled with an open "Call for Experts" on social media and the website.

3.3.2 Delphi Survey Round 1

Round 1 of the START Delphi Survey was presented in the following format (Figure 4):

1. Introduction: information about the project.
2. Objectives and Participation in the Delphi Survey: explanation of the objectives of the Delphi Survey, rules for participation and follow-up.

3. Disclaimer and Reminder: a statement for experts to comment on the issues and that the statements/questions do not necessarily represent the views or opinions of the START project consortium or the EU; acknowledgement of EU co-funding.
4. Personal data: a collection of data only for statistical purposes – nationality, gender, age, sector, level of expertise (Thermoelectrics, Materials and materials processing, Mining and mineral processing, Sustainable design (for recycling, for environment, eco-design), Renewable energy).
5. Delphi Statements: the statements of the Survey to be addressed by the experts (by agreeing or disagreeing and commenting).
 - The application of thermoelectric devices to transform waste heat into energy is the future of renewable energy and circular economy.
 - Sustainable thermoelectric devices would unblock the application of thermoelectrics in many fields, despite lower performance.
 - One solution-fits-all is not feasible for thermoelectric devices and applications.
 - Using tetrahedrite materials sourced from mining tailings recovery will mitigate the competition between thermoelectric and other electronic devices.
 - Applications using thermoelectric devices based on tetrahedrites will be on the market by 2030.
 - The START innovation ecosystem would be of interest to me.
6. Delphi Open Questions: the open questions of the Survey to be answered by the experts.
 - What kinds of devices or applications, in the short, medium and long-term, utilise thermoelectricity?
 - How will thermoelectricity impact our society? What are the pros and cons of its usage?
 - What's happening on the cutting edge of research in the field of thermoelectrics right now?
 - How can the creation and maintenance of a thermoelectrics value chain, dependent on recovery from mining tailings, be as flexible, scalable and adaptable as possible?
 - What are the potential market penetration barriers and the market opportunities for replication and market development of a tetrahedrite based TE value chain?
7. Delphi Multiple choice and ordering: multiple choice and ordering questions to be answered by the experts.

START

START project Delphi Survey Round 1

Disclaimer ✕
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Anonymous mode ✕
The anonymous option has been activated. As a result, your contribution to this survey will be anonymous as the system will not save any personal data such as your IP address.

Pages

Introduction **Objectives and participation in the Delphi Survey** Disclaimer and Reminder Personal data

Delphi statements Delphi open questions Delphi multiple choice and ordering Thank you for participating!

Views
[Standard](#) Accessibility Mode

Languages
 English ▾

Useful links
[START project website](#)
[The START project. Creating a sustainable supply chain for green energy harvesting products by Powder Metallurgy](#)
[START Factsheet](#)

Background Documents
[START_project_concept.png](#)

Figure 4: Delphi Survey Round 1.

3.3.3 Delphi Survey Round 2

Round 2 of the START Delphi Survey was presented in the following format (Figure 5):

1. Introduction: information about the project.
2. Objectives and Participation in the Delphi Survey: explanation of the objectives of the Delphi Survey, rules for participation and follow-up.
3. Disclaimer and Reminder: a statement for experts to comment on the issues and that the statements/questions do not necessarily represent the views or opinions of the START project consortium or the EU; acknowledgement of EU co-funding.
4. Personal data: a collection of data only for statistical purposes – nationality, gender, age, sector, level of expertise (Thermoelectrics, Materials and materials processing, Mining and mineral processing, Sustainable design (for recycling, for environment, eco-design), Renewable energy).
5. Delphi Statements: the statements of the Survey to be addressed by the experts.
 - Design, development and implementation of thermoelectric devices should focus more on reliability of operation than on performance.
 - An ultimate goal of thermoelectric devices for mass production shall be the focus on developing a device that fits a large variety of applications in a large temperature range.
 - If synthetic materials (e.g. synthetic tetrahedrite) show better physical and chemical characteristics than natural materials, then the former should be favoured into thermoelectric devices, independently of other benefits that natural materials might have.
 - The booming of thermoelectric applications still relies on the breakthrough of high performance materials with affordable costs. With the existing materials and manufacturing methods, new use cases are yet to be explored and might still be in the niche markets.
 - A renaissance of space-related applications might boost the development of thermoelectric energy harvesting technology. But it might not lead directly to large scale implementation in industry, due to the large difference in the working conditions and design principles.
 - A fully-fledged thermoelectric value chain based on tetrahedrites will not be in the market by 2030. However, for long term success, the core stages (e.g. material zT , functional devices, lower costs, proven operation) of this value chain need to be commercially and feasibility detailed by then.
6. Delphi Open Questions: the Open questions of the Survey to be answered by the experts.
 - What metrics should be used throughout the thermoelectrics value chain as commercial and feasibility indicators?
 - What regulatory factors could either facilitate or impede the deployment of thermoelectric technologies?
 - In how many year(s)/what timeframe could thermoelectric technologies become commercially competitive with other energy conversion methods?
 - Very high zT values arising from research activities do not help to grow practical thermoelectric applications. Should the community focus on thermoelectric materials with moderate zT and make commercial and feasibility studies based on

their inclusion to speed up commercialization and marketization of thermoelectric generators?

START project Delphi Survey Round 2

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Pages

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[Delphi open questions](#)
[Thank you for participating!](#)

1 Introduction

The EU co-funded project [START - Sustainable energy harvesting systems based on innovative mine waste recycling](#) (Grant agreement ID: 101058632), is developing a sustainable supply chain for green energy harvesting products and proposes a unique technological solution, based on a "waste material-waste heat to power" methodology for the development of sustainable and economically viable tellurium-free waste heat harvesting systems.

START aims at producing advanced sulphide thermoelements that incorporate discarded sulphide minerals in mining waste to replace current commercial tellurium-based thermoelements. While tellurium is an important raw material sourced outside of Europe, the tetrahedrite-tennantite mineral series that is used is relatively abundant in copper mine tailings and, at present, is an environmental hazard.

The START project concept can be summarised as follows:

Figure 5: Delphi Survey Round 2.

3.4 INTERVIEWS WITH EXPERTS

To tie the methodology and data collection, interviews with internal and external experts were done. These interviews were held 1-on-1 with the involvement of WP7 expert partners and one external expert serving START as a member of the Advisory Board. Interviews focused on thermoelectric-related questions based on both research and commercial aspects of the technology line and the START value chain. Past, present and future aspects were explored through questions and free dialogues during these sessions (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Interview with DTP Thermoelectrics.

4 DATA COLLECTION

4.1.1 Focus Groups #1, #2 and #3

Data from Focus Groups sessions was collected from answers to the main questions of interest to the START project below. A summary of the main aspects of the answers received is described following each question.

1. What are the big uncertainties of Thermoelectrics (TE) and materials for TE value chains? What could happen that changes the value chain?

Overall, the replies provided by experts to this question focus on the challenges and opportunities surrounding TE technology, emphasizing the need for addressing material costs, supply chain development, feasibility, and market awareness to drive broader adoption and application of the technology. The following main points were mentioned as the main uncertainties of thermoelectric value chains: Raw Material Price Volatility, Risk of Material Scarcity, Material synthesis (i.e. achieving good mechanical properties and stability at large-scale production), Device assembly and manufacturing process, Reliability (e.g. material degradation and failure) and Reproducibility of TE devices, Feasibility of Primary Production, Uncertainty in Energy System Restructuring, Use in Remote Areas, Lack of Value Chain for TE, Cost Dependency on Business and Need for Market Awareness.

2. What kind of applications do you see as potential and promising based on TE materials? By which year do you think such application could reach the market?

The discussion along this question highlighted the versatility and potential of TEGs across various applications, from waste heat recovery to special energy needs in challenging environments, with a focus on integration, efficiency, and market competitiveness. The following main applications and categories were selected as optimal by the participants: Applications for Waste Heat Utilization (e.g. exhaust and cogeneration systems, wearable devices and settlement of remote energy needs), Specialised applications such as space, defense, and remote areas with challenging environmental conditions (e.g. remote gas pipelines), Integration with IoT Devices and Component integration into more complex systems, Refrigeration, Domestic heating and biomass.

3. Do you know of any ongoing research or new results related to TE? Do you know of any new trends in TE?

Participants referred to the evolving landscape of thermoelectric technology, with a focus on addressing challenges in space exploration, waste heat utilization, manufacturing processes, and performance improvements. Research and trends identified include: Emerging Applications in Sensors and Wearables, Utilizing Waste Heat in Processes, Advancements in TE Manufacturing to reduce losses (e.g. additive manufacturing), Performance Improvements towards 15% efficiency, Reducing manufacturing costs, Improving environmental performance, Production of nanomaterials, thermoelectric polymers, and composites. It is worthy of mention that also a comment on START's proposed technology to produce thermoelectric materials from naturally occurring minerals was highlighted as novel on a global scale.

4. Do you believe that the future of TE could be based on tetrahedrites?

Comments to this question focused on the importance of diversification within industries and the potential of a specific technology or material, likely referring to tetrahedrite as the case of START, which seems to be undervalued. However, there's a general note of caution, indicating that tetrahedrite based TE devices might not be the highest-performing option, which could impact businesses. The discussion suggests that it's still early to draw definitive conclusions about the viability of potential applications, without extensive technological and market implementation first. While there is recognition of the importance of material choice, experts state that it's crucial to be aware of, and address all critical steps beyond the materials themselves to ensure the effectiveness and viability of tetrahedral group materials in TE applications.

5. Would you be willing to pay more for a sustainable TE device? How much more?

Participants found this a particularly interesting question. The replies highlighted the complexities of consumer attitudes towards sustainability and the importance of effectively integrating sustainability into product offerings to meet consumer preferences and market demands. The following aspects were emphasized: Sustainability, as a unique selling point, Price range that customers are willing to pay even for sustainable products to be taken into account, Pairing Sustainability with Other Factors to enhance its appeal and justify potential higher prices, Importance of identifying target consumer groups and finding spaces for sustainable products, such as thermoelectric devices in sport watches or computers. The example of electric vehicles was given as a good one to follow: an example where sustainability, such as driving in extra lanes, can provide additional benefits beyond just environmental considerations. Experts believe, as an estimation, that the acceptable price for TE modules should not exceed 1 EUR per 1W of electrical power produced. As a last comment, experts also hinted that solving specific problems will lead to commercialization of TE devices and that while sustainable TE devices may be more expensive initially, their adoption may increase as the market for thermoelectricity grows and sustainability becomes a more significant factor in decision-making.

6. Do you miss any elements from the START planned activities/focus?

In general, the participants believe that the actions defined within the START project framework are well planned and are set to cover many of the stages of a value chain (START concept, Figure 7). Despite this, they highlighted the importance that should be given to client engagement, application-driven approaches, market assessments, and a complete supply chain in advancing TE technology projects effectively as points of improvement that need dedicated actions. A few advices to complement the START activities include: Involving clients as stakeholders in TE projects, particularly in addressing main uncertainties and ensuring alignment with application-driven approaches; START shall be driven by specific applications; Market assessments per application are deemed essential to determine potential volume and viability; Business and finance figures are needed to support applications and bring together various branches effectively; Drafting an integrated supply chain, involving companies at different stages, and providing system integrator solutions; Reaching credible product levels between TRL 6 to TRL 9, indicating stability, durability testing and readiness for commercialization. Experts also mentioned that the START plan may need to place more emphasis on aspects related to the purification

and homogenization of minerals, on initial steps of the value chain. Another concern raised is the selection of suitable n-type materials and the complexity of connecting them with p-type materials (the process of binding or soldering the two materials may add complexity to the technology).

Figure 7: Original START concept.

7. What are your main doubts for the START approach?

When replying and discussing this question, participants mentioned the following aspects as main doubts for the development and implementation of the START tasks: the utilization of tetrahedrite as the selected mineral during processing and utilization due to its unproven effectiveness; The challenge in commercialising waste heat, or; The need of integrated devices and systems driven by good applications.

8. What are the benefits that you expect that you could gain/use from the START project? Any commercial ones?

In general terms, participants' comments highlight optimism about the potential of the START project to drive advancements in TE technology and its applications, seen as a potential huge push to the further development of TE products and projects. Participants expect that the START results will contribute to the enhanced visibility of thermoelectric technologies in industrial applications, to intensified demonstration of TE's market viability, to strengthened engagement with the TE community and remaining stakeholders, to the development of more low-cost, environmentally friendly TE solutions for high-temperature waste heat applications with significant implications for various industries. Regarding the last point, Vecarius (Focus Groups participant), expressed its interest in affordable TE modules.

9. Who (companies, research groups, field of expertise, etc.) could be interested in the START technological approach?

Experts agree that if the START thermoelectric technology initiative proves successful, and a good-performance TE module is developed, identifying launching customers or end-users for specific applications will be crucial. They mentioned the need to involve various

stakeholders as part of the value chain: Mining operators and other waste material providers, Material processing companies, TE device producers, System integrators, End-users for selected applications at different temperature ranges, Companies that previously dealt with TE modules but withdrew due to economic challenges, Companies that could potentially integrate TE modules into their systems once cost-effective options are available and Emerging companies that may seize economic opportunities presented by the availability of low-cost TE modules.

10. Would the appearance of a new, more efficient material, hinder START from becoming commercialised? If yes, what could we plan/do for avoiding that?

Overall, the discussion highlights the importance of close monitoring and assessing competition within various application segments of TE technology, considering both incumbent and emerging technologies, to mitigate risks and ensure successful commercialization efforts for START's tetrahedrite-based devices. Named risks include: Rising competition from other energy sources (including current and future ones) and Being outcompeted by other TE-family materials. As a final note, experts agree that efficiency versus cost would play a big role in giving the advantage to a specific material over the other, and that tetrahedrite can benefit in this equation.

4.1.2 Delphi Survey Round 1

Data from Round 1 of the START Delphi Survey was collected from answers and comments to the below main statements and questions of interest to the START project. A summary of the main aspects of the comments received is described below each question.

1. The application of thermoelectric devices to transform waste heat into energy is the future of renewable energy and circular economy.

Experts came to a general agreement that the implementation of thermoelectric energy production is one of the great possibilities to generate green energy and contribute to the circular economy. The responses highlight several perspectives on the role of thermoelectric devices in the future of renewable energy. Some believe TE will have a place in the family of renewable energies, with a focus on thermal energy harvesting for industrial digitalization, combined use of waste heat for electric power and domestic heating, with low and high-grade heat harvesting using TE seen as a priority, aligned with EU targets for sustainable heavy industry. The importance of utilizing waste heat, especially in the current context of

substantial waste heat generation, is emphasized for clean energy and energy circularity. Others expressed their concerns on the application of TE regarding cost-efficiency and, heat-to-electricity sustainable manufacturing. Furthermore, TE devices although acknowledged as one option for converting waste heat into electricity, are perceived as limited to specific niche applications.

2. Sustainable thermoelectric devices would unblock the application of thermoelectrics in many fields, despite lower performance.

In general, experts agree that the development and implementation of more sustainable thermoelectric devices, when compared to the current ones, would greatly change the way the technology is seen by end-users and society at large. Despite this, experts highlight a few bottlenecks that need to be solved before TE is implemented at large, including materials and device stability, aging effects, and the critical need for sustainability to justify investments in thermoelectric development. Cost, production methods, and material source sustainability play a crucial role in making thermoelectrics attractive for various fields and the primary barriers to large-scale adoption identified are performance (conversion efficiency), cost, and scalability, with an emphasis on the availability and non-toxicity of materials. While the technology is seen as holding promise for applications like powering IoT sensor networks, its limitations in generating sufficient electric power for many fields are noted. A final remark is that higher performance remains essential for adoption in various applications.

3. One solution-fits-all is not feasible for thermoelectric devices and applications.

Experts tend to agree that the best approach for the development of TE devices is not to develop one overall solution, but rather develop specific devices for specific temperature ranges. Experts state that temperature dependence of material and device performances, along with the need for design optimization, makes it challenging to achieve a "one solution-fits-all" approach. They list temperature range, cost, reliability, and customization options as factors that impact the design of thermoelectric generators. Experts also mention that applications vary in thermal load and environmental conditions, requiring a holistic consideration of materials and device architecture for optimal performance.

4. Using tetrahedrite materials sourced from mining tailings recovery will mitigate the competition between thermoelectric and other electronic devices.

The use of tetrahedrite materials for TE devices is rather divisive. The strategy of producing thermoelectric materials directly from waste mineral tetrahedrites is considered promising from the perspectives of sustainability, waste valorization, and critical materials management. The potential benefits identified include cost reduction compared to traditional mining and processing methods for other minerals and materials. However, experts also mention that the success of the START project in particular hinges on the complexity and cost-effectiveness of processing minerals, especially in terms of tailing recovery impact on thermoelectric generator efficiency, reliability, and reproducibility, which are not yet proven and require project results for a better assessment.

5. Applications using thermoelectric devices based on tetrahedrites will be on the market by 2030.

Experts agree that tetrahedrite based TE devices will hit the market successfully in the future, but they disagree towards the timeframe for that to happen. Some experts state that development of thermoelectric technology depends on the effort and resources applied, taking several years to develop from materials to devices. However, they also suggest that the key towards market implementation of a TE technology lies in matching promising materials with the right applications, considering factors like source and heat flux density, together with the operating temperature and the discovery of potential n-type materials to couple with the tetrahedrites. Tetrahedrite shows promise for low to medium temperatures applications, utilizing cost-effective materials, but competition with other mid-temperature materials like half-heuslers and skutterudites might hinder marketization. Finally, some caution is advised, as successful commercialization of TE devices is still to be assessed in the future as the survival of companies producing them is still uncertain as the last years have proven.

6. The START innovation ecosystem would be of interest to me.

Experts found that the START work and the value chain that it is developing, built around the use of tetrahedrites, would be of great interest to them. The project is viewed as an opportunity to contribute to sustainable thermoelectrics, waste heat recovery, and the generation of green energy from electronic devices produced through tailings recovery, which is a unique process. Experts emphasize the importance of successful development for further industrialization, involving various relevant players to meet performance, cost, scalability, integration, sales, and improvement requirements.

7. What kinds of devices or applications, in the short, medium and long-term, utilise thermoelectricity?

Experts' answers identify a broad range of applications for thermoelectric devices in various industries and sectors. In summary, they suggest that thermoelectric technology finds, or will find applications across various sectors, including industry, automotive, wearables, IoT, and space, with an emphasis on waste heat recovery, power generation, and electronic cooling. The applications include:

- Industrial Sector: Waste heat recovery systems in industries with considerable waste heat and power generation to provide energy to devices (e.g. safety devices in industry to prevent contact burns); Power supplies for district heating, heat

exchanger monitoring, pumping monitoring, construction monitoring, environmental sensors, and gas leakage sensors in remote places; Refrigeration.

- Wearable Devices and IoT: Application in wearable devices, such as smartwatches, IoT devices, and biomedical sensors; Microgenerators to power various components in the near future; Power supply for IoT sensors in the medium term.
- Energy Autonomous Systems: Powering sensors, remote systems, space (radioisotopes) power systems, etc.; Mention of electronic cooling and long-term power supply without maintenance.
- Space Applications: Mention of RTGs (Radioisotope Thermoelectric Generators) for space and remote power generation in special-purpose and rural domestic settings.
- Other Applications: Human-machine interface for thermal sensing and actuation, Cooling and low-temperature power generation technologies, Predictions for the future development of nanoscale heat recovery devices in industries like metallurgical, glass, or petrochemical; Use in electronic cooling, long-term power supply without maintenance, and waste heat recovery for remote power supply in IoT.

General Predictions forwarded by the experts:

- Short-term applications may include Peltier cooling.
- Medium to long-term applications include energy recovery from processes where efficiency is crucial, such as foundation industries, i.e. heavy industries.
- Long-term applications involve geothermal and solar-thermal power generation, as well as microscale thermal management.

8. How will thermoelectricity impact our society? What are the pros and cons of its usage?

Experts state that thermoelectric technology offers various advantages to societal applications, including off-grid capability, durability, and the ability to generate renewable energy in hard-to-reach places. As the technology can contribute to reducing the CO₂ footprint of industries, improve energy efficiency, and enable the recovery of waste heat, these are seen as of great importance for the future of society. Impact can also be seen in promoting the energy transition and reducing reliance on fossil fuels. Despite the benefits, namely that devices have a long life and require minimal maintenance, experts highlight some of the bottlenecks, their low efficiency, high costs, reliance on scarce materials and need for scalability as challenges that need to be addressed for widespread adoption and a significant positive impact on the environment.

9. What's happening on the cutting edge of research in the field of thermoelectrics right now?

Participants referred a number of research and innovation developments in the field of thermoelectrics. These include research, innovation and development works towards optimization of known materials, to enhance reliability, efficiency, and flexibility in demanding designs and system integration. Sustainable materials and flexible devices are current crucial areas of investigation, aiming for high-performance multilayer TEs operating across large temperature ranges. Some experts see thermoelectric modules utilizing

multilayer materials with a high figure of merit and proving economic viability are central concerns that need to see more investigation and efforts, as a main goal. There is a need for breakthrough technologies, and attention is turning more and more towards sustainable materials.

Other aspects of current TE research, are the emphasis in high zT materials and high performing devices, focusing on new active materials, bonding materials, and device testing. With these, the main goals are to increase efficiency, reduce manufacturing costs, and develop efficient heat transfer methods. While numerous materials show promise, integration issues and challenges in large-volume production hinder competitive pricing. Efforts also aim to lower the lattice thermal conductivity while maintaining a high-power factor, utilizing alternative materials and manufacturing methods.

Nanotechnology is also mentioned as one of the main research flagships as is the study of new materials while avoiding rare earth, toxic, or expensive elements, by employing nanostructuring or cascading devices. Flexible devices, new materials based on environmentally friendly elements, and new TEG design integration are ongoing priorities.

10. How can the creation and maintenance of a thermoelectrics value chain, dependent on recovery from mining tailings, be as flexible, scalable and adaptable as possible?

The success of START as a thermoelectric technology developing project, particularly in using mining tailings, hinges on factors such as achieving high efficiency, ensuring reliable material development for thermal energy harvesting, and maintaining a flexible composition of raw materials, as suggested by experts. For the creation of the value chain, key considerations include waste reduction through mining recovery, securing a stable supply chain, and focusing on the entire process from materials production to module and system assembly. Experts mention that the scalability of the technology will depend on developing cost-effective and efficient converters and automating production, which are very important development steps. Furthermore, it is suggested that collaboration with the right partners, an open society approach, and regular interaction within the full supply chain are needed to ensure success and adaptability in the evolving community. The use of mining tailings is seen as a sensible approach to reduce material costs in thermoelectric technology, that might give the advantage that START needs to create a unique value chain in Europe and worldwide.

11. What are the potential market penetration barriers and the market opportunities for replication and market development of a tetrahedrite based TE value chain?

Mentioned market barriers include unproven performance, low efficiency and thermal stability of tetrahedrites, high processing costs and difficult process, and the absence of identified market applications. The need for high efficiency and stability in thermoelectric materials, especially for medium temperature applications like transport and heavy industries is another barrier. The importance of convincing potential markets of the utility of tetrahedrite-based TE technology is emphasized by some experts, along with the need for testing in real-world applications. Cost competitiveness, manufacturing scalability, and efficiency are identified as critical factors for successful market entry.

On the other hand, there are also market opportunities mentioned such as using tetrahedrite as a non-toxic and sustainable material, recoverable from tailings, as a unique approach,

potentially pushing START forward and giving its value chain an advantage when compared to more traditional TE value chains.

12. In your opinion, what is mostly missing from thermoelectrics value chains to make them an alternative to energy production?

Experts identify as main gaps in thermoelectrics value chains the lack of good performance displayed by TE materials and devices, the lack of applications across different temperature ranges, missing end-users interaction and awareness for this specific technology, the need to step up commercialization efforts and lack of more devices' prototyping, testing and implementation.

4.1.3 Delphi Survey Round 2

Data from Round 2 of the START Delphi Survey was collected from answers and comments to the below main statements and questions of interest to the START project. A summary of the main aspects of the comments received is described after each question.

1. Design, development and implementation of thermoelectric devices should focus more on reliability of operation than on performance.

Experts tend more to disagree than agree with the statement, in the basis that both reliability and performance should be considered of equal importance in the development and

implementation processes of TE devices and technology, and should, therefore, see improvements at the same time. However, it is also mentioned that the importance of reliability and performance in thermoelectric devices varies based on end-user needs, so there are cases where reliability does take precedence over performance and efficiency, and while the latter are not TE's biggest selling points, there still needs to be criteria for performance. The example of waste heat conversion is cited, where reliability of operation is more important than performance. However, in scenarios with high heat costs, performance could be prioritized.

Ultimately, it is mostly agreed that a balance between reliability and performance is desired for a successful design and implementation of TE devices in its applications.

- 2. An ultimate goal of thermoelectric devices for mass production shall be the focus on developing a device that fits a large variety of applications in a large temperature range.**

A divisive statement that depicts the divergence of opinions about the development of devices that can be used across different temperature ranges. Arguments in favor of such an approach mention the current situation with the use of bismuth telluride (BiTe, one of the most common materials in TE devices, toxic and expensive), that it will be helpful to enhance the market demand and, consequently, the mass production of tetrahedrite-based TE and that waste heat is very variable and a transversal device could be implemented in several applications. On the other hand, arguments against an approach to develop one device that fits all temperature ranges mention that it would be better and more realistic to have different devices targeting difference applications, that most of the applications suit in a short temperature range, and that developing a broad range of devices, each fit for a certain range of temperatures, and all devices together covering a broad range of temperatures would be a better approach.

3. If synthetic materials (e.g. synthetic tetrahedrite) show better physical and chemical characteristics than natural materials, then the former should be favoured into thermoelectric devices, independently of other benefits that natural materials might have.

Opinions on the preference of synthetic materials over natural ones are scattered. While some experts offer arguments in favour, others offer arguments against this view. The first group states reasons including that performance and reliability are key and not the source of the material used, and that TE devices should always use the better cost-effective material to save cost on the system aspects, independently on the source of material. Naturally occurring minerals are characterised by a wide variety of chemical compositions and thus low repeatability of thermoelectric parameters. The cost of homogenising the physico-chemical parameters of natural minerals to make them suitable for production can be very high, even higher than the cost of synthetic materials.

These points are counterbalanced with the idea that if the difference is not that significant (and the performance of natural materials is within the expected range), nowadays other benefits as circular economy and sustainability are very critical in product development and quality/environmental certification, for example, that complex trade-off between costs, legislation and sustainability aspects and their respective weighting, that the scale of performance will dictate the winner. The benefits of using natural materials (e.g. lower environmental costs of manufacturing) may outweigh the gains of using synthetic materials.

Ultimately, it is mostly agreed that the selection of one over the other is a component of many factors (geological, environmental, material, application, etc.).

- 4. The booming of thermoelectric applications still relies on the breakthrough of high-performance materials with affordable costs. With the existing materials and manufacturing methods, new use cases are yet to be explored and might still be in the niche markets.**

Participants mostly agree that TE is still scarcely applied and that there are opportunities still to uncover in many fields. A widespread use of TE seems to be hindered by the current material choices for TE devices, since they are not robust or efficient enough (e.g., contacts are too fragile and prone to thermal degradation, obliging the designers to work with bypass valves and other complicated system issues). Disagreement comments state that the performance of known materials is already quite sufficient for mass production of devices and for wider implementation in end-user applications.

- 5. A renaissance of space-related applications might boost the development of thermoelectric energy harvesting technology. But it might not lead directly to large scale implementation in industry, due to the large difference in the working conditions and design principles.**

Experts tend to believe that space applications of TE devices can be a flagship for the widespread use of the technology in other applications. Despite this positive outcome, it is important to note that working conditions and requirements between space and terrestrial applications are quite different. Disagreement comments state that both space and

terrestrial applications require high efficiency (high-zT) materials. Space applications can support non-recurrent engineering costs that terrestrial applications can benefit from, and call for a universal technical solution that can be used in any field.

6. **A fully-fledged thermoelectric value chain based on tetrahedrites will not be in the market by 2030. However, for long term success, the core stages (e.g. material zT, functional devices, lower costs, proven operation) of this value chain need to be commercially and feasibility detailed by then.**

Experts mostly agree that the journey from material development to practical applications in thermoelectric technology is a lengthy and ongoing process. While they also consider tetrahedrite as a source material as a potential option for large-scale applications, they're not the only material and still need to prove their positive performance in devices and applications. Since tetrahedrite based TE devices and systems haven't been commercially shown at large, focus should be on the development of proven materials instead before 2030.

7. **What metrics should be used throughout the thermoelectrics value chain as commercial and feasibility indicators?**

The considerations for evaluating thermoelectric devices and systems encompass various factors as suggested by experts:

Commercial & Economic indicators:

- Return on Investment, Number of Years to achieve Return on Investment
- Levelized Cost of Energy
- Energy payback time
- Produced kWh/cost of TE production
- Cost, Cost-benefit-ratio of the overall device, Power-cost ratio
- €/W as CAPEX for TEGs
- Total cost of ownership including upstream and downstream technologies (heat exchangers, connectors, power electronics, power storage, etc.)
- Nominal power per costs of production (W/€ for end-users)
- Device lifetime/price
- Thermo-emf
- Base/Raw Materials quantities available for TE applications

- CO2 savings
- LCA indicators such as initial CO2 emissions per W, reliability on critical or non-renewable raw materials

Feasibility and Performance indicators:

- Useful lifetime, Service life in working hours
- Performance, Efficiency in energy conversion
- Toxicity
- zT for materials
- Power factor (or output), Power generation of the TEG
- Maximum temperature for thermal stability
- W/K for devices
- Stability and reliability factors
- Power/heat density
- Working temperature
- Thermal efficiency

8. What regulatory factors could either facilitate or impede the deployment of thermoelectric technologies?

The following regulatory factors were mentioned by experts as those of having the possibility to impact the deployment of thermoelectric technologies:

- Thermoelectric energy systems and production should be clearly defined as green energy.
- Political factors such as more restrictive regulations or bans on the import of raw materials (like Bi, Te, Ge (as a recent case from China)), Legislation regarding tailings recovery/reprocessing of raw materials, Regulations on elimination of hazardous materials such as Pb, the allowed use of insoluble lead compounds, like PbTe and PbS (these are not absorbed and have low toxicity), in TE devices, Seeing similar support as photovoltaic energy (e.g. subsidies or fiscal advantages for producers as well as final consumers, increased funding for research).
- Economic factors such as energy prices (high energy prices favour TE application), Reduced prices or bigger discounts to acquire TE devices, Carbon taxes, Taxes on waste heat (which now is free), Low efficiency of TE devices (due to a lack of concept regarding their structure).
- Societal factors such as a Common desire for the renewable and green energy products and, Public support to communication towards adopters.

9. In how many year(s)/what timeframes could thermoelectric technologies become commercially competitive with other energy conversion methods?

Most experts believe that TE devices, systems and technologies, relying or not on tetrahedrite, could become commercially competitive with other energy conversion methods in between a 5- and 15-years' timeframe. Their reasoning for this includes the decision on which energy conversion methods/technologies to be used (making it so that it should take at least 10 years to surpass photovoltaics), that it also depends on the application (with

some applications being earlier or later competitive), but that TE technologies should focus on niche applications where other competitors cannot become competitive in 10 years (competition with thermodynamic cycles will remain very challenging in the next years). Finally, experts state that for most TEGs the current TRL is 5-6, meaning that they still need 5 more years of R+D+I to reach TRL 7-8 and then 5 more years to reach TRL 9 (fully commercial).

Yet, some experts state that this timeframe could be reduced to 2 years (e.g., the START case, if a device is developed in 2024, then it could be implemented in 2-3 years) or could be as much as 50 years (this being due the lacking or low level of financial support for the development of thermoelectric technology, at current levels of economic investment and political framework. The discovery of novel TE materials or the discovery of a widely usable application can greatly change the latter timeframe to a more reduced one of around 10 or less years.

One last comment of relevance is that TE technology can only be competitive with other energy methods if it focuses on waste heat recovery.

10. Very high zT values arising from research activities do not help to grow practical thermoelectric applications. Should the community focus on thermoelectric materials with moderate zT and make commercial and feasibility studies based on their inclusion to speed up commercialization and marketization of thermoelectric generators?

Generally, experts agree that the thermoelectric community and TE value chains should focus more on materials with moderate zT and develop commercial and feasibility studies for these, instead of hoping for the “golden goose” of TE materials and/or application. They see that this is the best way forward since it can give a maximum of applications for the general society, since device design and sustainable manufacturing are as important as the zT , incentivizing more efforts to be made in the near future towards these aspects. Experts also believe that commercial and feasibility studies should be developed as early as possible for materials and, that the engineering of a complete TEG, with less focus on TE materials, could help speeding up the realization of reliable harvesters. Focus on reproducibility, engineering and material issues (e.g., contacts, T-gradient stability), as well as the belief that cheap materials should be the focus as research, are also highlighted. that zT is important but reliable integration in functioning systems is indispensable. An interesting comment states that systems developed with lower zT materials will afterwards be easy to upgrade with higher zT materials, if (when)ever they become available, supporting another comment that zT is important but reliable integration in functioning systems is indispensable.

On the other hand, experts against the value of this statement say that high zT material values are essential in research and for practical applications, that there still needs to be a continuous focus on improving efficiency (since low performance will be unacceptable in some applications), that a full bandwidth of research is required (i.e., people for the visions and the high zT , people for technological feasibility and people for device integration), that commercialization can be very challenging with poor power performance, that together high zT , contact resistance and stability are also needed. In their view, high zT and commercialization should be sought together.

4.1.4 Interviews with Thermoelectric experts

As an additional part of the data collection methodology, interviews were held with experts. These were one-on-one interviews with thermoelectric industry experts to better understand their innovation and exploitation experiences regarding development and commercialization of TE devices and systems. These experts work within TE-related companies, with international experience, so this was considered as a great opportunity to get specific information on business and marketization aspects, that can serve as a learning platform for the development of the START ecosystem.

The interviews were done online, where engagement and discussion were driven by questions and answers. The main discussion points during these interviews were:

- Previous and current experience with TE development and implementation
- Previous and current experience with TE commercialization and marketization (Return on Investment, Reasons for success and failure, Business models, Pricing, Costs and Revenues)
- TE trends and market trends affecting technology and energy
- Value proposition, communication and awareness on TE technology
- Financial and Technological metrics
- Regulatory or compliance challenges
- Cooperation and engagement with value chain members and end-users
- Feedback received from customers
- Application sectors

The interviewed experts expressed their views and opinions along some questions raised to see how START can address any challenges of exploitation and commercialization. Experts reasoned about previous efforts in using tetrahedrite for TE devices and why they failed commercially, but they also stated that TE technology (even if using bismuth telluride) can flourish in dedicated albeit niche markets (e.g., heating and cooling seats for the automotive industry, space). The challenges presented regarding the use of tetrahedrites were its low efficiency and choice of application, that despite lower costs of tetrahedrite, there are other costs that are also important (ceramic plates, manufacturing, system as a whole), thus it might not be enough in itself to keep the system costs down. Experts also commented on how regulatory support or lack thereof can facilitate or hinder the development and implementation of TE technology.

Experts also made some recommendations for the START project, namely, that the use of tetrahedrite in new devices is very welcome due to its cost-effectiveness, that tetrahedrite-based materials do not need the highest zT and naturally produced tetrahedrite do not need to have the same efficiency as a synthetic tetrahedrite to be commercially successful, that focus shall be on the overall power generation side of TE rather than on efficiency itself, making as much power as possible and that Combined Heat and Power applications are a winning solution for TE. Other recommendations mention that smaller components work better than bigger components in TE, even if offering less power and that focus of applications should be on those with lower footprint.

As a last note, experts also recommend that the START team should find a niche application for its devices at first while coupling it with a bigger application to target two markets at the same time: the niche market would allow generation of money early on so that resources can be used to scaling up and proving the technology for the bigger application.

5 RESULTS

The implementation of the foresight exercises supported inventories on two main aspects that are relevant for the elaboration of the START innovation and exploitation strategy. These are the creation of a general value chain of novel tetrahedrite-based thermoelectric devices and the mapping of uncertainties for enabling a flexible, scalable and adaptable business case design and commercialization strategy for START. This section summarises work and results on the value chain development introducing the framework built for START, followed by an analysis of currently important aspects and activities, and by the uncertainties of START in particular, and of thermoelectrics in general, that impact the full implementation of activities along the value chain. A review of flexibilities in the value chain is also provided with potential adaptations and relevant recommendations. The chapter introduces the review of mapped applications and the LogFrame approach applied for START with the aim to further support the definition of basics for a flexible, scalable, adaptable mineral-derived value chain for novel thermoelectric devices with the ultimate purpose to enhance the expected value of the START project, potential business cases and associated commercialization strategies, contributing to the short, medium and long-term sustainability of the technology line.

5.1 VALUE CHAIN DEVELOPMENT

5.1.1 The START Value chain framework

The initial START value chain has been developed taking into account the overall project concept including the main methodological steps:

Figure 8: START Project concept.

The general **START Value Chain framework** is similar to other TE-based value chains incorporating primary and supporting activities as per the below graphics:

Figure 9: START Value Chain Framework.

The framework was established based on the foresight exercises, following the model of Michael Porter's Value Chain analysis (Porter, 1985). It aims at mapping the full chain of business activities from the initial receipt of materials through the market delivery of the future product and service deriving from the START project results. The five primary activities have been tailored to the START approach and – based on the present knowledge of the consortium - support activities have been mapped, too. The framework will be used for monitoring START activities and evaluating their assumed efficiency during the project execution. It will also serve as a basis for enhancing efficiency of sub-activities beyond the project, resulting in keeping costs as low as possible, thus increasing market competencies, while it will also be used during inventories for roadmapping START potential for mid- and long-term future. The analysis may also support identification of linkages, dependencies, points for crucial decision-making and for supporting adequate orientations. The focus will be on sub-activities that are considered to be relevant at certain stages of the project: some of the sub-activities are already highly relevant at the present project progress, some will become more relevant at a later stage, while some may remain at the level of assumption at the project end or even beyond.

5.1.2 START Primary activities

According to the inventory made based on the applied model, the primary activities of the START Value Chain include the below activities (further broken down into sub-activities). These elements are introduced broadly at this stage and may be further specified, modified, and adjusted by the START consortium during reviews, including dedicated workshops and other sessions for progressing further towards a successful project implementation.

Inbound Logistics

1. *Raw material sourcing (mine waste & other, for n- & p-type tetrahedrite):* In line with the START project objectives, raw material sourcing shall encompass the utilization of mine waste containing tetrahedrites ensuring sustainability and repurposing discarded resources to contribute to circularity thus minimizing environmental impact and EU's dependency on sources available outside of its territories.
2. *Material synthesis, processing & production:* Refining tetrahedrite ore into high-performance thermoelectric materials demands well-defined and well-executed synthesis, processing, and production techniques, ensuring optimal material properties for efficient integration into thermoelectric devices that are suitable for applications with different requirements (i.e., low or high temperature environments).

Operations

1. *Component (pellet) manufacturing & Module assembly:* Manufacturing thermoelectric components involves precision assembly of pellets, optimizing their configuration for maximum efficiency and cost competitiveness. Module assembly integrates the components into functional units, ensuring flawless integration for optimal device performance.
2. *Application specific system integration and installation:* Tailoring thermoelectric systems to specific applications demands careful planning and execution of integration and installation processes with the aim of ensuring seamless and durable operation and optimal performance in the relevant environments, meeting well-known user requirements at competitive costs.

Outbound Logistics

Distribution, logistics, guidance, and support: Delivery of outputs to customers include processes that involve systems for product storage, collection and distribution to customers. This includes managing a company's internal systems and external systems from customer organizations. Outbound logistics in the START value chain framework encompass distribution, logistics, guidance, and support:

- Distribution networks shall be designed ensuring timely delivery of thermoelectric devices to customers.
- Logistics: transportation and storage processes shall be designed ensuring minimized delays and optimized inventory management.
- Guidance and support services are crucial to assist customers in understanding and utilizing thermoelectric solutions effectively, enhancing overall satisfaction, fostering long-term relationships also being sources of feedback as input to the optimization of other activities such as technology development, marketing and sales.

Marketing & Sales

Activities include advertising and brand building of the START products and services, which seek to increase visibility, reach a targeted audience and communicate why a consumer should purchase them.

1. *Technology specific:* Marketing and sales efforts may be designed with technology-specific focus on highlighting the unique features and advantages of tetrahedrite-based thermoelectric devices. This includes educating potential customers about the innovative technology, its efficiency, reliability, and versatility in various applications.

2. *Application specific:* Marketing and sales strategies can also be designed based on the perspective of the targeted application - in which the START device may be built in - with tailored messaging on well-meeting its specific needs and requirements. This involves understanding customer pain points, demonstrating how tetrahedrite-based thermoelectric devices can address these challenges effectively, and showcasing similar successful case studies and applications to potential clients.

Service

Activities targeting customer service and product support, ensuring the establishment of long-term relationship with those who have purchased the product or service, and activities strengthening reputation.

1. *Maintenance:* Maintenance services shall ensure the continued optimal performance of tetrahedrite-based thermoelectric devices. This includes regular inspections, troubleshooting, and repairs to address any issues promptly, minimizing downtime and maximizing efficiency.
2. *Waste management & recycling methodology:* Services with focus on minimizing environmental impact by implementing efficient waste management practices and recycling methods. This involves responsibly handling discarded materials, recycling components where possible, and adhering to sustainable practices to reduce waste generation throughout the product lifecycle. In the case of START, this aspect is crucial to be well-addressed.

5.1.3 START Support activities

The basic inventory of the START supporting activities are outlined in the figure below along with the scalability aspects of both primary and supporting activities, that will be addressed in the following section 8.1.4.

Figure 10: START Value Chain - Support activities & scalability.

Support or secondary activities ensuring the fine performance of primary activities have been gathered and outlined and broadly customized for START as per the subdivisions explained below.

Firm Infrastructure

Company infrastructure serves as the basis for the entire operational framework, including the core activity, legal, general management, administration, accounting, finance, public relations and quality assurance activities. The START-specific infrastructure requires the below main items.

1. *Laboratory facilities:* In the case of START product development, laboratory facilities may be essential spaces for research and development activities, facilitating innovation and experimentation to advance tetrahedrite-based thermoelectric technology.
2. *Production facilities:* In our showcase, production facilities may be integral to the company infrastructure, providing the necessary infrastructure for manufacturing and processing tetrahedrite materials into high-performance thermoelectric modules and/or devices efficiently and effectively.
3. *Non-technical infrastructure (i.e., legal, admin, finance, etc.):* Non-technical infrastructure, including legal, administrative, and financial departments, supports the overall operations of the firm. This includes managing legal compliance, administrative tasks, financial operations, and strategic planning to ensure the smooth functioning and long-term sustainability of the company.

Human Resource Management

Human Resource Management in general includes activities such as hiring, training, building and maintaining an organizational culture and maintaining positive employee relationships. In the case of START the following sub-groups of personnel may be relevant and be overthought for the value chain.

1. *Team with experience and knowhow in the field of TE materials:* A skilled and knowledgeable team specialized in thermoelectric (TE) materials shall be assembled. This team may comprise of experts in materials science, physics, and engineering with extensive experience in TE technology. Their expertise is essential for advancing research, development, and production of tetrahedrite-based thermoelectric devices, ensuring continuous innovation and improvement within the value chain.
2. *Training team:* A dedicated training team may be of high importance for equipping employees with the necessary skills and knowledge to well-perform in their roles. Depending on the START product and/or service, training programs may cover various aspects of TE materials, manufacturing processes, quality control measures, and safety protocols. By providing ongoing training and development opportunities, this team ensures that employees remain up-to-date with the latest advancements and best practices in the field, fostering a culture of continuous learning and improvement, thus contributing to a strengthened market position.
3. *Non-technical HR:* These functions include recruitment, employee relations, performance management, and strategic workforce planning, ensures the smooth operation of administrative processes, compliance with labour laws and regulations, and the development of policies and procedures to support the company's goals and objectives. Their role also includes the fostering of positive work environment, promoting employee well-being, and implementing effective HR strategies.

Technology Development

Technology Development is a critical aspect of advancing tetrahedrite-based the TE technologies, ensuring innovation and competitiveness along the START value chain. This section focuses on key strategies aimed at driving technological advancements and maintaining a competitive edge.

Beside research and development, activities such as IT management and cybersecurity, as well as anything that builds and maintains an organization's use of technology may fall in this category.

1. *Reinvestment in R&D*: Continuous reinvestment in research and development (R&D) activities is of great importance for pushing the boundaries of the START technology. This involves allocating resources towards exploring new materials, enhancing manufacturing processes, and improving device performance. By prioritizing R&D investments, the company can stay at the forefront of technological innovation, driving growth and differentiation in the market.
2. *Strategic partnerships*: Forming strategic partnerships with academic institutions, research organizations, and industry collaborators is incremental in accelerating technology development, enabling access to diverse expertise, resources, and funding opportunities, fostering synergies that move innovation forward. Through strategic alliances, the company can leverage complementary strengths and capabilities to tackle complex challenges and capitalize on emerging opportunities in the TE business environment.
3. *IPR management*: Effective management of intellectual property rights (IPR) is essential for safeguarding innovations and maintaining a competitive advantage. This involves identifying, protecting, and commercializing proprietary technologies through patents, copyrights, and trademarks, i.e., that are partially or fully generated by START. Additionally, establishing licensing agreements and enforcing IPR policies helps mitigate the risk of infringement and ensures that the company's innovations remain protected. By strategically managing IPR, the company can secure its position in the market and extract value from its technological advancements.

Procurement

Procurement involves finding new external vendors, maintaining vendor relationships, and negotiating prices and other activities needed to obtain materials and resources used to build a product or service.

1. *Long-term relationships with a stable and loyal pool of vendors*: Building long-term partnerships with reliable vendors ensures a consistent supply of quality materials, fostering efficiency and stability.
2. *Compliance with high quality standards*: Adhering to strict quality standards guarantees that procured materials meet required specifications, enhancing product integrity and customer satisfaction.

5.1.4 Scalability of the START Value Chain

An important aspect of commercialization is the scalability of the START approach and value chain. Scalability's main points have been outlined in Figure 10. This should be reviewed by the research and commercialization teams at every relevant, crucial stage reached during technology development. Its elements are to be considered during decision-making, aiding products and technologies arising from the START project and ecosystem to become viable and cost-competitive options for the future and for fulfilling project objectives to the maximum extent possible.

Successful scale-up may require the planning and adjustment of all activities including primary and supporting activities and along each sub-activity. Such exercise may be performed at a later stage of the START project or beyond the project duration, already during commercialization of products or services deriving from the project results by foreground owners including the START Service Company, which will be created before the project finalizes.

Value chain mapping and analysis

Focusing on the START value chain framework, mapping and an in-depth analysis have been launched with the help of the foresight exercises. Information has been collected on: Stakeholders, Gaps, Issues and Cons, Trends, and Pros, that the START approach in particular, and thermoelectrics in general have. Until now, due to the nature of the START project concept and to the present level of technology readiness of potential results, the outcome of foresight exercises showed greater attention towards the below activities and aspects.

Along the project evolution and the maturation of the START technology, further elements will be put into scope, while activities already mapped and analysed will be reviewed and refined, if necessary. A summary of the interim results of the value chain mapping is presented below in the order of present importance and attention.

- 1) Technology Development
- 2) Material Synthesis, Processing and Production
- 3) Component Manufacturing & Module Assembly
- 4) System Integration & Installation and Maintenance
- 5) Marketing & Sales
- 6) Waste Management and Recycling

Technology Development

Stakeholders: Researchers and Scientists; Government Agencies; Educational Institutions; International Collaborators; Investors and Financial Institutions.

Gaps, Issues and Cons: Lack of Breakthrough Technology; Limited Efficiency; Failure to Translate Promising Materials to Devices; Insufficient Investment in Research.

Trends: Optimization of Known Materials; Research on Sustainable Alternative Materials; Investigation of New Active Materials; Development of Bonding Materials; Increasing Efficiency; Utilization of Nanotechnology.

Materials Synthesis, Processing & Production

Stakeholders: Mining companies, Geological Surveys; Technology developers; Device manufacturers; Material companies; Educational Institutions; Investors and Financial Institutions; Companies and research groups involved in processing various types of waste and minerals.

Gaps, Issues and Cons: Need for High Efficiency and Stability; Availability and Non-Toxicity of Materials; Gap Between Promising Materials and Device Implementation; Challenges in Sustainable Mass Production; Reproducibility of Material Properties; Barriers to Performance in High Temperatures.

Trends: Optimization of Known Materials; Development of High zT Materials and Devices; avoidance of Rare Earth, Toxic, or Expensive Elements; New Materials Based on Environmentally Friendly Elements; Focus on Efficiency, Cost Reduction, and Environmental Performance; Exploration of Nanomaterials, Polymers, and Composites.

Component Manufacturing and Module Assembly

Stakeholders: Technology developers; Device manufacturers; Engineers and Technologists; Material companies.

Gaps, Issues and Cons: Cost Efficiency and Sustainability; Economy of Scale and Material Supply; Performance and Efficiency; Scalability and Integration; Sustainability and Material Origin; Device Stack Optimization; Reliance on Scarce and Toxic Materials; Manufacturing Process Uncertainty; Challenges in Material Combination and Assembly; Focus on Material Properties vs. Assembly; Interfacing and Mechanical Properties.

Trends: Flexible and Bendable TEG Designs; High zT Materials and Device Improvement; Reduced Manufacturing Costs; Alternative Manufacturing Methods; Material Improvement and Element Avoidance; TEG Design and Integration; Efficient Low-Grade Heat Conversion; Scalable Manufacturing and Cost-Effective Production; Additive Manufacturing Automated Assembly.

Pros: Development of devices with improved performances will increase the overall impact on society, mainly promoting a larger use of thermoelectric solution.

System Integration and Installation & Maintenance

Stakeholders: Engineers and Technologists; Energy Industry; Automotive Industry; Aerospace Industry; Standards Organizations; Investors and Financial Institutions.

Gaps, Issues and Cons: Sustainability, processing costs, and cost-efficiency are critical factors in TE development; Maintaining functionality and reproducibility of TE devices is essential for their practical use; Technical challenges such as materials and device stability, ageing effects, and system integration need to be addressed; Challenges persist even after integrating TE materials into modules, including building efficient heat exchanger systems and power conditioning; Consideration of application targets is crucial, especially regarding reliability and reproducibility, as industrial applications face specific challenges related to cycles and environmental stress; Assembly and extensive testing are vital for validation before commercialization, ensuring the reliability and performance of TE devices.

Trends: Developing efficient methods for heat transfer from technological processes is a priority; TEG (Thermoelectric Generator) design and integration are important for effectively implementing TE systems; Thermal energy harvesting using TE is seen as a means to enhance the digitalization of the industry, particularly in powering IIoT (Industrial Internet of Things) sensors; TE is considered a top choice for harvesting low-grade heat due to its suitability for such applications; There is a focus on developing high-performance multilayer TE systems capable of operating across a wide temperature range for improved efficiency and versatility.

Pros: Off-grid; Enabling IoT in hard-to-reach places will reduce CO₂ footprint of many industries with all the consequences related to it for society; Durability, long-term viability.

Marketing & Sales

Stakeholders: Investors and Financial Institutions; End-users from selected applications (e.g. metallurgical plants, glass factories, ceramics, petrochemical and cement plants, Industrial

applications with constant 24/7 operation, converting geothermal and solar energy, refrigeration, buildings, etc).

Gaps, Issues and Cons: Lack of awareness of TE options in potential market niches; High manufacturing costs and market volatility; Concerns about the cost-effectiveness of TE devices and their unproven affordability; Need for higher TE performance in many applications to drive adoption; Limited electric power generation capability in some applications; Lower efficiency compared to alternative heat-to-power solutions; Uncertainty about the long-term durability of TE devices; Competition from other renewable energy technologies with higher efficiency rates; Future trends may reduce waste heat generation, impacting the role of thermoelectrics; Limited suitability for large-scale power generation compared to other recovery systems; Current TE devices for room temperature applications rely on rare materials; Concerns about low efficiency, mitigated if TE devices can be made cost-effective; Assembly costs and other factors contribute significantly to overall costs; Challenges in generating significant power from wearable TE devices, with power recovery from the body being very low.

Trends: Emphasis on proving the economic viability of thermoelectric generators; Focus on reducing costs to make thermoelectric technology more accessible; Exploration of diverse applications for thermoelectric devices; Growing interest in flexible and wearable thermoelectric devices for applications in electronics, health monitoring, and military uses; Integration of thermoelectric devices into IoT devices for energy harvesting in remote or low-power scenarios; Continued application of thermoelectric technology for waste heat recovery in industries like automotive, industrial processes, and power generation, contributing to energy efficiency and sustainability; Exploration of thermoelectric devices for medical applications, including wearable health monitors and implantable devices; Ongoing research and development to incorporate thermoelectric cooling into consumer electronics to address thermal management issues; Increased investments from governments, research institutions, and private industries to accelerate the commercialization of thermoelectric technologies.

Pros: Reliable solid-state energy conversion: Thermoelectric devices offer consistent energy conversion without the need for moving parts; Ideal for powering IoT sensor networks and as an alternative to Li-Ion batteries: Thermoelectricity can provide sustainable power for small devices and serve as an eco-friendly alternative to traditional batteries; Has a place in renewable energies: Thermoelectric technology can contribute to renewable energy initiatives; Supports EU sustainability targets for heavy industry: It aligns with EU goals for reducing energy consumption and CO₂ emissions in heavy industries; Utilizes waste heat: Thermoelectric systems can harness large amounts of waste heat for clean energy production, promoting energy circularity; Long lifespan, low maintenance, and scalability: Thermoelectric devices offer durability, minimal upkeep, and adaptability to various scales of operation; Improves energy efficiency and reduces emissions: By converting waste heat into usable energy, thermoelectricity enhances overall energy efficiency and reduces emissions; Versatile applications in different temperature ranges: Thermoelectric technology can be applied across a wide range of temperatures and environments; Possible energy storage: Generated electricity can be stored in batteries for later use; Prevents waste of energy and resources: By capturing and utilizing waste heat, thermoelectric systems help minimize energy wastage; Compact, silent, and durable: Thermoelectric devices are compact, operate quietly, and have a long-lasting design; Transformation of cooling systems: Thermoelectricity has the potential to revolutionize cooling systems, making them more environmentally friendly; Enhances system

efficiency despite current performance limitations: Integration of thermoelectric technology can naturally enhance system efficiency, even with current device performance constraints.

Waste management and Recycling

Stakeholders: Environmental Advocates; Standards Organizations; Recycling plants; Electronics industry.

5.2 UNCERTAINTIES AND DOUBTS

Uncertainties are aspects of START in particular and of thermoelectrics in general that impact the full development and implementation of the many steps of the value chain design. It is important to understand the uncertainties in the value chain design and the doubts that experts express regarding it, to be able to make the START value chain more reliable, trying to fix the weaker points. This is then done in the form of recommendations. The following uncertainties and doubts for the START (and thermoelectric) value chain stages were identified.

Material Synthesis, Processing and Production:

- Sustainable materials (e.g. tetrahedrite) are secondary to performance, cost and scalability. Therefore, **even by using tetrahedrite, if the START devices are not performing well, are costly or have scalability issues, the value chain will be unreliable.**
- The START technological and business case is **dependent on the ease of converting mining tailings into a useful material in terms of costs**, which might end up not being enough for commercial success. Processing of the tetrahedrite minerals may turn out to be too complicated and ultimately too costly.
- **Sulphide instability of tetrahedrites can impact the processed materials thus affecting the next stage of the value chain** (development of devices).
- START assumes that the production of thermoelectric materials directly from tetrahedrites can significantly reduce production costs and make the technology competitive with others. However, **a clear assessment in this respect will depend on the results of the project.**
- Doubts about the **zT values of natural tetrahedrite when compared to synthetic tetrahedrite**, for the choice of most appropriate material. On the one hand, naturally occurring minerals are characterised by a wide variety of chemical compositions and thus low repeatability of thermoelectric parameters. The cost of homogenising the physico-chemical parameters of natural minerals to make them suitable for production can be very high, even higher than the cost of synthetic materials. On the other hand, the benefits of using natural materials (e.g. lower environmental costs of manufacturing) may outweigh the gains of using synthetic materials. **The outcome is a component of many factors (geological, environmental, material, application, etc.).**
- The amount and type of mineral that could be used in the formulation of TE materials could **be too low to make feasible/effective the use of mine tailings**, and in particular their retrieval and concentration.
- The **material synthesis requires good mechanical properties and good stability at large scale production**, which might not be obtained with tetrahedrite.
- **Purification, homogenisation and control of the composition of the minerals is a challenge** for processing.

- If the **cost of the material is a substantial part of the cost of the system**, the **design is wrong. Always pick the better material and save cost on the system aspects.**
- **Current materials are not robust or efficient enough: contacts are too fragile and prone to thermal degradation**, obliging the designers to work with bypass valves and other complicated system issues.
- **Tetrahedrites are one option** for large scale applications, **but not the only one.**

Component Manufacturing & Module Assembly:

- Doubts about the **performance of tetrahedrite-based TE modules.**
- Temperature dependence of materials and devices performances, as well as design optimisation **make having a START solution that fits all applications not possible.**
- **Temperature range for selected applications might not be adequate for tetrahedrite based TE devices.**
- Doubts about the possibility to have a **customizable TEG layout.**
- Doubts on **how the use of tailing recovery impacts TEG efficiency, reliability, reproducibility and costs.**
- The tetrahedrite based thermocouple does not have a sustainable n-type, the disadvantage of tetrahedrite is the lack of a similar n-type. **Connecting the p-type and n-type materials could be difficult – binding-soldering the two materials may make the technology quite complicated.**
- **Manufacturing scalability is a concern.**
- **Lack of commercial devices**, such as thermoelectric generators, **capable of implementing tetrahedrite-based thermoelectric modules for large-scale use.**
- **Missing durability tests/prognosis of the final products.**
- **Natural tetrahedrites are still too weak as a material for a large-scale application**, showing issues with obtaining a stable chemical element and the soldering, isolation, the coating of material to save it from oxidation.
- **The weak point of thermoelectric devices is low performance**, which hinders their mass application.

System Integration & Installation and Maintenance:

- TE can be applied in very different temperature ranges, and it is **necessary that the used materials can be stable in each operation conditions.**
- **Doubts about the correct integration of START devices into existing systems due to compatibility, size, weight, and overall system optimization.** System might not allow for a good coupling of the TE device, depending on the design.
- The regulatory landscape for thermoelectric technologies is still evolving. **Uncertainties regarding standards, certifications, and regulations may influence the development and deployment of thermoelectric devices**, especially in safety-critical applications.
- **Long-term durability and reliability of START devices.** Reliability issues, due to using the device between two very different temperatures, one very hot and the other very cold and having thermal and mechanical constraints.
- Doubts on the **practicality of tetrahedrite-based modules at a broader scale.**

- **START is missing the coupling system, the heat exchangers for a full system integration and transfer into application.** One of the main sources of costs for TE is the system for the thermal exchange.
- There are no tests yet for **thermal management**, which should be done.

Marketing and Sales:

- Heat is probably not considered into the cost models since it is free. **But there are doubts if this will always be the case.**
- **Cost factors** (related to the context of use).
- **Uncertainty on the START timeline to have a fully-fledged value chain by 2030.** To develop a full technology (from materials to devices) requires several years and means.
- **Too low efficiency and therefore limited markets** (current and prospective) **discourages private investments**, which might hinder the funding for continuing developing the START value chain. **Availability of funding** (public and private) **after the project is not certain.**
- **Doubts about matching the START device to the right application** (source and heat flux density) in order to make an impact.
- **Doubts on the feasibility to achieve cost-competitive production, scalability, and affordability for end-users.**
- **The competition with other emerging technologies may impact the market acceptance and adoption of START thermoelectric devices.**
- **Public perception safety, environmental impact, or unfamiliarity with the technology could be a bottleneck for marketization.**
- **Waste heat recovery is not easy to commercialize.**
- The START ecosystem based on tetrahedrites will face the **competition of other TE families** (e.g. skutterudites or half-heuslers, or zintl) **or other energy production equipment.**
- **Doubts if the START ecosystem can be built with the support of START project partners only.** It might **need to integrate external stakeholders to fill gaps in the value chain development.**
- To be realistic in getting to the market, **systems large enough** (giving enough power) **are needed to be a measurable impact.**
- **Doubts on the feasibility of reaching TRL-6 by the end of the START project (2026).** Future development of a START value chain will also be dependent on **the level of financial support for the development of thermoelectric technology.** At current levels of investment, it could be 50-100 years until commercial readiness. At support levels like shown for photovoltaics – it could be even less than 10 years.

5.3 FLEXIBILITY IN THE VALUE CHAIN, SPIN-OFFS, ADAPTATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Value chain flexibility corresponds to the capacity of changing aspects within the many stages of the value chain to obtain similar or better results. Flexibility and adaptation can become a need depending on the future development of R&D, problems in material sourcing, device production, system integration or finding reliable applications and willing end-users, for example. Mapping points of flexibility help to keep the value chain resilient, responsive and cost-efficient.

Recommendations and considerations can be made to allow space for this flexibility to come into practice as soon as the opportunity or need arise. The following flexibility points and recommendations were identified for the value chain stages:

Material Synthesis, Processing and Production:

- Tetrahedrites is one promising option for the low to mid temperature range applications, but the START ecosystem should **consider other materials as well** to substitute tetrahedrite for better cost/value outputs.
- START ecosystem devices could **become more resilient and adaptable if done with different source materials and flexible compositions**.
- N-type materials are a possible bottleneck for the development of the devices. Consider **exploring alternative approaches to produce also n-type materials** from the tetrahedrite group or from other minerals with comparable physicochemical properties.
- Electronic devices produced from tailings recovery/valorisation are products with interest to sustainability and LCA areas. The START ecosystem could **consider the design and development of other type of devices from tetrahedrites** for different applications (in and outside of a TE value chain).
- The START ecosystem needs to **secure supply of quality tetrahedrites from more than one mine** site's tailings with uniformity/equivalent properties and in the necessary quantities, also from different geographical areas. It is also necessary that **they can be processed by similar conditions and parameters**.
- The START ecosystem needs to consider the **recovery of relevant elements from consumer electronics waste**, to further support the sustainability aspect of its value chain.
- The START ecosystem should **create and implement sustainable and effective fabrication protocols to process materials** (e.g. a bottoms-up chemical synthesis could be of interest).
- Consider the **use of synthetic tetrahedrite instead of natural** tetrahedrite.
- At the same time that START invests in the development of a tetrahedrite-based TE value chain, it would add to its resilience to **also explore high zT materials**. Commercialization can be very challenging with poor power performance.
- The START ecosystem needs to **study resolving less common challenges from engineering and materials including contact resistance and Temperature gradient stability**.

Component Manufacturing & Module Assembly:

- The START ecosystem needs to **guarantee that the developed TE material and device is reliable** (withstanding assembly processes and operations with demanding temperature gradients and harsh environments).
- The main focus should **not be on finding the most efficient material, but to ensure a complete assembly into a large scale TEG** tile, that can easily be combined to a larger area to cover containers or other large surfaces or that can be fitted in between hot and cold surfaces withstanding humidity, vibration and temperature cycles without delaminating between the material and the packaging/conductive parts of the system.
- The START ecosystem needs to **pursue on purpose design of its TE devices**, adapting the design of TE devices to its final selected applications. Adding to this, **different**

configurations should be studied, and device architecture must be considered for optimal performance.

- The physics-guided device co-design (from heat transfer and electrical impedance matching) could be a **feasible way to guide the TE device fabrication and contribute to sustainable thermoelectrics**, that the START ecosystem could bring into reality.
- The START ecosystem **needs to have**, directly or indirectly through third parties, **access to rapid and mass manufacturing of materials and devices.**
- The START ecosystem should **invest in investigating new processes** that could substitute currently more expensive processes in manufacturing and assembly (e.g. 3D printing).
- **Focus on developing both reliability and performance of devices** should be a priority for the ecosystem. The decision on which is more important depends on the particular application of the device. In the case of a device for the conversion of free waste heat, performance and efficiency appear to be less important in relation to reliability. However, in situations where the cost of heat is high, performance may take priority over reliability.
- The START team **should develop its own criteria for performance evaluation**, even if the focus is more on reliability than on performance of devices.
- START **should consider thermal efficiency as one of the main criteria of success** of its devices. If thermal efficiency is low, devices will never recover the energy that goes into fabricating the recovery system itself.
- **The START ecosystem can begin with a design, but since thermoelectric is a very flexible technology due to its very high power efficiency, the design can be later adjusted for different applications.**
- The START ecosystem **could aim at the development of a range of TE devices covering small temperatures at a time, but covering a big share of temperature range globally.** It would benefit the ecosystem to have different devices targeting different applications, even if different materials are used for different temperature ranges.
- The START ecosystem **needs to invest in device design and sustainable manufacturing.**
- **The engineering of a complete TEG, with less focus on TE materials, could help speeding up the realisation of reliable harvesters.**
- The START ecosystem **needs to invest heavily in reproducibility** of the devices.
- It is not possible to develop one device that fits all temperature ranges, TE devices are dedicated to specific temperature range applications and cannot be optimized for a large temperature range. This **calls for the development of a number of TE devices based on different materials to cover as much part of the temperature spectrum as possible, thus raising applications.**

System Integration & Installation and Maintenance:

- The START ecosystem should continue to **study different materials, aiming to find a material that could operate at low and medium temperature ranges** efficiently.
- The START ecosystem TE devices can **replace classic mechanical devices such as heat pumps and generators.**
- The START ecosystem needs to **find partners focusing on system integration** with START devices in end-users' applications.

- The START ecosystem needs to also **invest in developing its own heat exchangers** or other energy conversion equipment.

Marketing and Sales:

- TE costs are (also) associated with the source of the materials, therefore **using tetrahedrites or other cheap and abundant materials** is a great solution for cost-competitive TE devices. The START ecosystem should in any case **study new materials and new processing and assembly processes** to continue to reduce costs. **Reducing costs at all levels** from materials to application devices needs to be investigated.
- The START ecosystem must **pursue a scale up and automation of production built on mass manufacturing to reduce labour input**. This step **needs to be implemented after immediate results of the project**.
- The selected end-user commercial application(s) should be **built on mid-range temperature material devices, better suitable for terrestrial applications**.
- The START ecosystem needs to **map the risk of being outcompeted** by incumbent technologies or alternative solutions within an application segment.
- The lack of large-scale application of TE technology can open a large market potential for START devices. The team should **study several markets, develop devices and integrate systems** for those markets.
- An application area with high potential are **areas where it is not easy to get electricity, mostly at remote areas** and standalone situations. This would mean a START-based supply chain of very high value.
- The START ecosystem needs to **invest resources in raising and increasing awareness of the market for TEs**, especially towards the industry.
- The START ecosystem needs to **create a comparison between its TEG and other renewable energy sources**.
- The START technology application must **ensure competitive payback time to the customer**. Seventy-five percent (75%) of the total waste heat power capacity that TE could capitalize on requires less than a 5-year payback – 3 Euros per Watt, System cost, power conditioning + Insulation (1-2 Euros per Watt). An estimation of **no more than 1 Euro per 1W of electrical power** would be an acceptable TE module price for START.
- When (and if) the development is successful, **further industrialization will have to comprise other parties, to respond to performance, cost and scalability requirements as well as to enable integration, sales and further improvement**.
- The START ecosystem needs to **engage with other manufacturers**. The results from this part of the project may meet the interest of electrochemical batteries producers, among others, extending the potential for commercialization and business. A finetuned supply chain will **bring together interested industrial partners** who were not directly connected to thermoelectric and bring a device architecture to market that can be quickly adapted to different application needs.
- If the START ecosystem succeeds in developing and implementation a value chain around waste-heat energy, this **would help the whole community and would make thermoelectricity regarded again as something that can solve problems**. It would give a **great boost to the popularity and marketability** of START as well.
- The START ecosystem needs to **market its TE device as something that is “set and forget”**. The end-user should be able to get the device, integrate it into the system (e.g.

attaching the TE device to a pipe) and it should work continuously. If the START value chain can reach this with sustainable materials, this should be a breakthrough for the technology.

- The START ecosystem needs to **find applications that are outside of niche markets**. If thermoelectricity remains a niche market, people will go for the cheaper thing, but if thermoelectricity goes for a big market, the only possible devices will be the sustainable ones.
- The START ecosystem should be **built on a fully digitized supply chain**: automating processes, reducing manual labour, etc.
- The START ecosystem **needs to invest in low-temperature thermoelectric heat converters**, which have a huge demand.
- The START ecosystem **needs to plan and align its resources to meet an approximate timeline achieving TRL 7-8 in 5 years and TRL-9 in 10 years**. The shorter these periods can become, the better, but they might require more human and financial resources.
- Both space and terrestrial applications require high efficiency (high- zT) materials. **Space applications can support non-recurrent engineering costs that terrestrial applications can benefit from**. The START ecosystem **needs to engage and follow the space sector**.
- **Applications in higher temperatures**: the yield is crucial, translating into an economic saving next to a CO₂ reduction. Although pressure to reduce energy consumption is increased, the relative impact of a TE solution is limited unless implemented at full scale.
- **Applications in lower temperatures**: energy yield is very limited, hence the application shall be linked to a specific use of the electricity locally, such as IoT. This requires the development of this specific function as well in the form of an integrated device.

5.4 APPLICATIONS

Throughout the exercises, experts commented on the applications of thermoelectric devices. Several potential applications were mapped and are listed below. These are also considerations of pathways that a START value chain could follow to extend its marketability.

- Wearables: used in biomedical sensors and smartwatches for health monitoring.
- IoT: Employed in safety devices, power supply, smart sensors, thermal controllers, and sensor networks.
- Power Sources: ranging from miniature (milliwatts) to large power sources (hundreds of watts), enabling autonomous small-scale power generation.
- Automotive Industry: utilized in cars for energy harvesting and power generation.
- Industrial Facilities: applied in facilities with significant waste heat and temperature differences, such as furnaces, cooling stations, foundation industries, ships, and others.
- IT Central Systems: used in servers for efficient thermal management.
- Household Equipment: implemented in household appliances like fridges, ovens, and TVs for energy efficiency.
- Refrigeration and Cooling: used in refrigeration, cooling, and low-temperature power generation technologies.
- Peltier Coolers and TEGs: employed in small applications such as chips, lasers, fridges, and other electronics.

- Geothermal and Solar-Thermal Power Generation: utilized in power generation from geothermal and solar-thermal sources.
- Micro Distributed Generation: Implemented in micro-scale thermoelectric generation systems.
- Thermal Management: Used in cooling/heating systems where maintenance and size are significant factors.
- Micro Combined Heat and Power (CHP) Applications: Employed in generation, distribution, and storage systems.
- Domestic Heating with Biomass: Applied in domestic heating systems, with thermoelectric generators integrated with biomass burners.
- Markets with Unreliable Grids: Suitable for markets where the grid is not reliable, such as Nordic countries.
- Domestic Heating: Used for domestic heating applications, with potential thermal power conversion efficiencies ranging from 1 to 10 kW.

5.5 LOGFRAME

As an additional exercise, the LogFrame (Logical Framework) approach was used for START to support the definition of basics for a flexible, scalable, adaptable mineral-derived value chain for novel thermoelectric devices with the ultimate purpose to enhance the expected value of the START project, potential business cases and associated commercialization strategies.

The initial START LogFrame table reflects assumptions and plans based on the most current, interim findings of the project. It is building on results fed in by research work packages, taking into account the overall objectives of the START project as well as the business needs of commercial partners. Its four rows define long- to short-term objectives ranging from top to bottom. The LogFrame may be used starting from the top – driven by the goal, while it can also serve for supporting inventories starting from the bottom -driven by newly obtained START results. Along the project evolution, assumptions and consequently, plans may change upon new research outcomes of START as well as upon potential changes in the TE market environment. These can be reviewed along the table that may support the project success.

START LogFrame	Project Summary	Indicators	Means of Verification	Risks & assumptions
Goal	Fully successful exploitation of the START project results both on short and long term	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> potential business cases and associated commercialization strategies TE ecosystem establishment 	<p>Successful market entries</p> <p>Steady market growth of TEGs</p>	External factors: - unforeseen circumstances (i.e., War, pandemic)
Outcomes	Successful business models for different commercial applications	Temperature specific business models for applications- at least 5 applications (1 for low and 1 for high temp)	Acceptance by all value chain actors	Unforeseen risks upon performing PESTEL analysis
Outputs	Flexible, scalable, adaptable mineral-derived value chain for novel thermoelectric devices	Defined and available alternatives for substitution of each value chain actors -		
Activities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Foresight exercise Serious Game 	Focus groups sessions, Delphi survey (2 rounds) Serious game		

Figure 11: START LogFrame for a flexible, scalable, adaptable mineral-derived value chain for novel thermoelectric devices.

6 CONCLUSIONS AND FINAL RECOMMENDATIONS

START is advancing a unique thermoelectric value chain based on the use of tetrahedrites that are sustainably sourced materials. This report highlights how this approach is seen from the side of experts, through the implementation of foresight-adapted methods and tools that had resulted in interactions with experts on the components of the future START value chain. Thanks to these exercises, a number of pros, cons, trends, applications, uncertainties and flexibilities in different points of the START value chain are identified. Together, they will contribute to the creation of a more flexible, scalable and adaptable value chain.

This report contains essential elements for the current and future development of the START project, ranging from considerations for change to recommendations for improvement. Since these affect different parts of the value chain, which include different stakeholders, it is recommended that a wide range of researchers and people affected by TE value chains read this report carefully. There are connections and possible implications with technical work, that may affect the development of the START value chain already at this point.

The value chain structure presented in this report is built under the banner of a flexible value chain. In this way, the creation of different value chains, supported by the end goal of different applications can be easily adapted.

At the time of writing, START has selected two directions of applications as focus for its activities. These will be assessed in the next steps of Work Package 7, which will focus on measuring industrial viability and economic potential, defining an innovation agenda, create a roadmap for commercialization and establishing sustainability plans. These aspects will be tied with the creation of the START Service Company.

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